

Polymers in biosensors – a review

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Manuscript received 13 November 2000, revised 23 May 2001, accepted 20 July 2001

Biosensors offer enormous potential to quantitatively estimate a wide range of analytes in health care, chemical process industries, food industries and environmental monitoring. Polymers play an important role starting from the manufacturing of the electrodes to the immobilization process of the biomaterials. This review concentrates on the use of polymer films in the development of advanced biosensors. The functions of polymer film, e.g. removal of interference, immobilization of biocomponent etc. and deposition of polymer films on the sensor surface are discussed thoroughly.

Introduction

A biosensor is defined as 'a compact analytical device incorporating a biological or biologically derived sensing element either integrated within or intimately associated with a physicochemical transducer. The usual aim of a biosensor is to produce either discrete or continuous digital electronic signals which are proportional to a single analyte or a related group of analytes¹. Later, in the first authoritative meeting on biosensors held in 1986 in London by Royal Society, a biosensor was defined as 'a device that recognizes an analyte in an appropriate sample and interprets its concentration as an electrical signal via a suitable combination of a biological recognition system and an electrochemical transducer².

Leland C. Clark, Jr.² reported the first biosensor in 1956. His concept became commercial reality in 1975 with a successful launch of glucose analyzer. The four principal transducer classes are potentiometric, amperometric, optical, and other physicochemical. Potentiometric devices measure the accumulation of charge density at the surface of an electrode, an example being an ion-selective field-effect transistor (ISFET) for an ion such as sodium or a gas such as carbon dioxide. Amperometric sensors monitor currents generated when electrons are exchanged between a biological system and an electrode, an example being a blood glucose sensor. Optical biosensors correlate changes in concentration, mass, or number to direct changes in the characteristics of light. Other physicochemical sensors monitor biological interactions through changes in enthalpy, ionic conductance, and mass. Clark³ first introduced 'enzyme electrode' for glucose. Guilbault and Montalvo⁴ were the first to detail a potentiometric enzyme electrode. They developed a urea sensor based on urease immobilized at an ammonium-selective liquid membrane electrode. The biosensor

took a further evolutionary route in 1975, when Divis⁵ suggested that bacteria could be used as the biological element in *microbial electrodes* for the measurement of alcohol. A major breakthrough in the *in vivo* application of glucose biosensors was reported by Shichiri *et al*⁶ who described the first needle-type enzyme electrode for subcutaneous implantation in 1982. The BIAcore (Pharmacia, Sweden) launched in 1990 is based on Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR) technology described by Liedberg *et al*⁷.

Numerous research work have been published on a variety of biosensors with diverse applications exploiting enzymes, antibodies, nucleic acids, cell receptors, microbes in electrochemical, optical, piezoelectric and thermometric transducers⁸. The major application areas of biosensors are health care, food, environmental monitoring⁹, and process industries¹⁰.

An amperometric biosensor consists of a bioactive layer with/without polymer, an electrode and a signal processor. A schematic is shown in Fig. 1. The biochemical layer typically converts the analyte into other chemical species, which are sensed and transformed into an electrical signal by the transducer. The bioactive materials limit the lifetime, sta-

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of a typical biosensor

bility, reproducibility, calibration etc. The first biosensors are often called *enzyme electrodes* and were first described by Clark and Lyons³ for determination of glucose. Glucose biosensors are based on the fact that the enzyme glucose oxidase (GOD) catalyzes the oxidation of glucose to gluconic acid, and itself being reduced to GODH. In the early biosensors oxygen was used as the oxidizing agent which oxidizes GODH back to GOD. The consumption of oxygen was followed amperometrically by electrochemical reduction at a platinum electrode. The glucose oxidation reaction catalyzed by glucose oxidase is

At the electrode : $\text{O}_2 + 2 e^- + 2 \text{H}^+ = \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$

A voltage of -0.7 V was applied between the platinum cathode and the silver anode, sufficient to reduce the oxygen, and the cell current, which was proportional to the oxygen concentration, was measured. The concentration of glucose is proportional to the decrease in current. Later on many modifications came up which involve oxidation of GODH to GOD either directly at the electrode or through a mediator and glucose can now directly be measured on a modified carbon paste electrode or electropolymerized electrode using a palm-top reader.

Polymer films

Polymer films have been used in biosensors to protect the electrode surface from fouling, to block interferences, to immobilize the biocomponent, to entrap or incorporate a mediator, to extend the linear range of the biosensor. It is interesting to note that all commercial applications have employed polymer films to make the biosensor practical¹¹. Polymer films are categorized as conducting, nonconducting, and composite polymer films. Methods for film fabrication include solvent casting, electropolymerization and adsorption. Conducting polymer films are widely used, often to enhance electron transfer characteristics. Nonconducting films are frequently used for their permselective characteristics. Composite films offer the strength of blending the favorable characteristics of more than one film.

Conducting polymer films

Conducting films are incorporated in biosensors to facilitate electron transfer from biocomponent to the electrode surface, for the incorporation of mediators and in the immobilization of enzymes. A limitation of conducting films is that they may interact with chemical species or oxygen to produce deleterious effects. Conducting polymer films such as polypyrrole, polythiophene, polyaniline¹² are capable of conducting electronic charge. For analytical applications

polyacetylene, polypyrrole, polythiophene, poly-3-alkylthiophenes, poly(*p*-phenylene), and polyaniline¹³ are the most important polymers. Conducting polymer films can be divided into two categories, electronically conducting polymers such as polyacetylene^{14,15} and redox conducting polymers¹⁶. The polymers can be produced chemically or through electrochemical polymerization. The biomolecular interaction capabilities of polymers are easily modified by attaching functional groups to the polymer backbone. In a recent work, a range of sulfonated aromatics was incorporated into polypyrroles to form dyes. The ability of these dyes to complex metal ions such as aluminum or copper¹⁷ can then be used to advantage. These dyes also undergo selective interactions with proteins, and this has been exploited in development of other conducting polymer sensing technology¹⁸. Electron transfer mediators¹⁹, enzymes²⁰⁻²², and antibodies²³⁻²⁵ have also been incorporated into new biochemical sensors (Fig. 2a).

This process may be described as an $\text{E}(\text{CE})_n$ mechanism in which monomer oxidation is an electrochemical process (E), radical-radical coupling is a chemical process (C), and chain propagation is another electrochemical process (E) (Fig. 2b). The last two processes are repeated indefinitely²⁶. The study indicated that high monomer concentration, high supporting electrolyte concentration, and high current densities (or potentials) all increase the rate of chemical coupling and therefore improve the electropolymerization on electrodes.

In some cases, polymeric precoatings can facilitate electrodeposition of the conducting polymer. When the electrode substrate was precoated with nafion, electrodeposition of the conducting polymer was facilitated. The sulfonate charge on the nafion backbone acts as a counter ion for the initial layers of polypyrrole, knitting the conducting polymer to the electrode surface. Conducting polymer coatings undergo oxidation/reduction processes at moderate potentials.

A biosensor with an electropolymerized conducting polymer film was constructed by Cooper and Hall²⁷. Entrapment of glucose oxidase in a polyaniline film grown on a platinum electrode was carried out via electropolymerization at pH 1.1. The low pH conditions yielded improved conductivity of polyaniline. The conductive polymer in this case facilitated electron transfer from a biocomponent to the electrode surface. Glucose oxidase was used because it tolerated the low pH conditions.

Reagentless enzyme electrodes have been developed by the covalent bonding of enzymes using redox mediators and/or coenzymes on the sensor surface to prevent contamination of the sample by sensor components. Additionally, mini-

Fig. 2. (a) Electropolymerization of pyrrole, (b) electrochemical polymer chain propagation. Monomer oxidation is an electrochemical process, radical-radical coupling a chemical process, and chain propagation another electrochemical process. E_{app} is applied potential (Ref. 26).

aturization and mass production of enzyme electrodes require techniques for biosensor assembling avoiding manual deposition procedures. The electrochemical deposition of conducting polymer layers occurs at the surface of an electrode independent of its size and form. The morphology of the conducting polymer films can be adapted to exclude co-oxidizable compounds from approaching the electrode surface, thus improving the selectivity of the amperometric enzyme electrodes.

Most of the amperometric biosensors described until now are constructed either by crosslinking a suitable redox enzyme within a polymeric gel on the electrode surface or by assembling a preformed enzyme-containing membrane on top of the electrode. Two major drawbacks are reported. Since the active sites of redox enzymes are in general deeply

buried within the protein shell, direct electron transfer between enzymes and electrode surfaces is rarely encountered. This is particularly true for enzymes, which are integrated within non-conducting polymer membranes in front of the electrode surface. The electron transfer is usually performed according to a 'shuttle' mechanism involving free-diffusing electron transferring redox species, for example, the natural electron acceptor O_2 or artificial redox mediators like ferrocene derivatives²⁸, osmium complexes, quinones. The second drawback is the difficulty in assembling of an enzyme membrane and an electrode. Consequently, the next generation of amperometric enzyme electrodes has to be based on immobilization techniques, which are compatible with microelectronic mass production processes and easy to miniaturize.

Functionalized conducting polymers for the covalent binding of enzymes :

Conducting polymers like polypyrrole, polyaniline, polythiophene can be obtained by electrochemical polymerization either potentiostatically, galvanostatically or by means of multi-sweep experiments²⁹. Polymer films with defined thickness and morphology can be made by controlling the charge transferred during the electrochemical polymerization process, and parameters like temperature, monomer concentration, polymerization potential or current, as well as the concentration and nature of the supporting electrolyte. Hence, conducting polymer films show interesting properties concerning the decrease of the influence of interfering compounds due to their size-exclusion and ion-exchange characteristics^{30,31}.

The use of functionalized conducting polymer films is inevitable for the integration of bioselective compounds and/or redox mediator in the conducting polymer. The possibilities of functionalization of conducting polymer layers are shown in Fig. 3³². Functionalized monomers may be synthesized and subsequently polymerized along with the non-functionalized monomer. The already-grown conducting polymer film can be modified by means of heterogeneous reaction sequences.

Entrapment of enzymes within electrochemically-grown conducting polymer films :

This is unique method of entrapment of the enzymes within the growing polymeric network during the electrochemical polymerization process³³. The mass-transfer characteristics will depend on the diffusion of the substrate through the conducting polymer film leading to a dramatic dependence of the signal on the film thickness, the morphology and porosity of the conducting polymer film²².

Fig. 3. Various routes for the preparation of functionalized conducting polymers and subsequent covalent binding of enzymes : (a) functionalization of already grown polymer films, (b) polymerization of functionalized monomers, (c) copolymerization of functionalized and nonfunctionalized monomers, (d) copolymerization of functionalized and nonfunctionalized monomers of different type, (e) copolymerization of monomers of different types and subsequent functionalization (Ref. 32).

Entrapment of GOD with electropolymerization of pyrrole in a recent study carried out in our laboratory improved the performance of a Prostate Specific Antigen (PSA) sensor (Fig. 4).

Poly(*o*-aminophenol) was electropolymerized by Miland *et al.*³⁴ on a carbon paste electrode after dispersing uricase and HRP (horseradish peroxidase) for uric acid selective biosensor. Cyclic voltammetry was used to characterize the

Fig. 4. Response of a PSA sensor when GOD was immobilized by pyrrole electropolymerization on the working electrode. The figure shows responses for 0, 4, 15 ng/ml PSA concentration in human blood serum.

permselective characteristics of the polymer layer.

Water-soluble β -(aminoalkyl)pyrrole derivatives can be linked to IO_4^- -oxidized glucose oxidase³⁵ with formation of Schiff bases where a CHO group from GOD was condensed with NH_2 and subsequently reduced to the respective secondary amines by means of NaBH_4 (Fig. 5a, GOD not shown). The modification of GOD with water-insoluble pyrrole derivatives can be performed in a phase transfer reaction with individual enzyme molecules entrapped within the water pool of inverse micelles³⁶ (Fig. 5b). The pyrrole-

Fig. 5. Synthesis of pyrrole-modified glucose oxidase : (a) in aqueous solution, (b) in organic solvents (Ref. 36).

modified enzyme can be copolymerized with pyrrole to 'enzyme-loaded' conducting polymer films (Fig. 6) showing a significantly increased immobilized enzyme activity.

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of an amperometric biosensor with a pyrrole-modified enzyme copolymerized with pyrrole (Ref. 32).

Nonconducting polymer films

Nonconducting polymer films are incorporated into biosensors to prevent interferences, to prevent fouling of the electrode surface by proteins and other substances, to immobilize the biocomponent, and to entrap mediator so that it does not leach away. Non-conducting films formed by electropolymerization techniques show characteristics of molecular self-assembly. The typical film thickness for non-conducting polymer films formed by electropolymerization is about 10 nm.

Sasso *et al.*³⁷ developed a biosensor using a platinized reticulated vitreous carbon (RVC) electrode with immobilized glucose oxidase and an electropolymerized poly(1,2-diaminobenzene) (DAB) film that drastically reduced interference from L-ascorbate, urate, and L-cysteine and prevented fouling of the biosensor by proteins in blood serum. Additionally, thermal studies performed on electrodes with immobilized glucose oxidase that used carbodiimide for covalent bonding or glutaraldehyde for crosslinking demonstrated that increased thermal stability was obtained. Enzyme activity was maintained for one and one-half months with daily use. The poly(1,2-DAB) film was less stable than the enzyme (by about one week) and required repolymerization. Sarkar *et al.*³⁸ used polyethylenimine (PEI) in the working electrode paste for amino acid/protein biosensor and this increased device stability and reproducibility. A study of polymer coated glucose biosensor in our laboratory revealed that nafion gives considerably greater response than poly-L-lysine (Fig. 7).

Malitesta *et al.*³⁹ immobilized glucose on platinum electrodes by electropolymerizing 1,2-DAB (*o*-phenylenediamine). The film exhibited permselectivity in that ascorbate, a common interference in physiological systems, was blocked. Barlette *et al.*⁴⁰ constructed a glucose biosensor

Fig. 7. Comparison of response of GOD electrodes, coated with nafion and poly-L-lysine for immobilization of GOD. Enzyme loading is 100 mu/electrode

using an electropolymerized phenol film to immobilize glucose oxidase subsequent to allowing adsorption onto the surface of a platinum electrode. Detection of glucose was via H_2O_2 generated by the oxidation of glucose oxidase and was monitored at 0.9 V (vs SCE). Phenol derivatives including 3-nitrophenol, pyrogallol, 4-hydroxybenzene sulfonic acid, and bromophenol blue were also electropolymerized, but phenol itself produced the most suitable films.

Composite polymer films

In many cases composite membranes formed from two or more different types of polymers give better properties than the individual polymers. Koopal *et al.*⁴¹ reported the use of glassy carbon disk electrodes onto which platinum was sputtered and a mixture of agarose solution and latex suspension was applied to create a porous membrane. Subsequently, electropolymerization of the monomers was performed galvanostatically in aqueous solution to construct a composite film on the electrode. Immobilization of glucose oxidase was carried out by agitating composite membranes in a solution of glucose oxidase. Amperometric response to glucose over a range of 1–60 mM was obtained.

Polymer film fabrication

Techniques for producing polymer films on electrode surfaces that will be considered include solvent casting, spin coating, electropolymerization, and adsorption.

Solvent casting :

In this approach a polymer film is formed by evaporation of a polymer solution placed on the electrode surface. The method has limited use since it is difficult to obtain complete and uniform coverage, especially when one is forming a very thin film.

Spin coating :

To prepare film-covered electrodes by spin coating⁴², the polymer is dissolved in an appropriate solvent and microliter quantities of the polymer solution are dropped onto the electrode which is mechanically fixed to a spinner that rotates the electrode at a high speed such as 4000 rpm. The film is air-dried as it continues to spin for several minutes. Typically, numerous monolayers must be applied to obtain films free from pinholes¹⁵. Spin coating is used extensively in the electronics industry.

Electropolymerization :

Polypyrrole film was used for glucose oxidase immobilization in our laboratory (unpublished work) and it gave satisfactory response and better stability of the electrodes. A thin film of polypyrrole was deposited along with glu-

cose oxidase on the working electrode by electro-polymerization of the monomer from an electrolyte of the monomer and glucose oxidase. Pyrrole (0.4 M) was dissolved in 0.05 M phosphate buffer (pH 7) with 0.1 M KCl containing glucose oxidase (250 U/ml). Cyclic voltammograms (6 scans) were taken (0–1.0 V) with a scan rate of 50 mV/s using a platinum reference electrode. The unique feature of this work is that the electropolymerization was made on a screen-printed electrode (rhodinized carbon) using platinum as reference electrode. The construction of biosensor using a conducting polymer film that contained a mediator and used to immobilize an enzyme was described by Tabakovic *et al.*⁴³. Glucose oxidase was immobilized in a polycationic polyvinylpyridine polymer that contained ferrocene as mediator.

When the transfer of electrons at the electrode-solution interface that result from the passage of current through the solution, is manifested as reduction or oxidation reactions in which certain reactive intermediates are produced, chain polymerization may result⁴⁴. As per Faraday's law current flow determines the rate at which polymer formation occurs. The total amount of charge transfer dictates the amount of polymer generated. For surface films, the thickness of the film of polymer is determined by the total charge transferred.

Some typical electrode materials for electropolymerization include glassy carbon, platinum or gold²⁹. Though good films with acceptable adherence are obtained on gold and platinum electrodes, the potential use of these metals is not as high as that for glassy carbon and the film is stripped by the evolution of hydrogen or oxygen. Indium-tin oxide-coated glass, titanium, aluminum, mild steel and brass are some other important electrode materials. Poor quality films are produced on aluminum¹³.

Various methods for polymer film formation via electropolymerization are potential cycling methods, fixed potential techniques, pulsed potential approaches, and galvanostatic techniques⁴⁵.

Electropolymerization offers many advantages such as the ability to coat very small or irregularly shaped electrode surfaces with a polymeric film, the ability to control film thickness based upon the amount of charge passed in the case of conducting films or by self-regulation in the case of non-conducting films, the ability to influence the polymerization rate and the nature of the film via the applied potential used during electropolymerization. In addition, electropolymerized films have been successfully employed in the blockage of interferences that would otherwise un-

dergo oxidation at the electrode surface and foul electrode surfaces.

Adsorption :

Adsorption can roughly be divided into two classes : physical adsorption (physisorption) and chemical adsorption (chemisorption). Physisorption is usually weak and occurs via the formation of van der Waals bonds, occasionally with hydrogen bonds or charge transfer forces. Chemisorption is much stronger and involves the formation of covalent bonds.

Physical adsorption of a polymer film onto an electrode is a simple technique for film formation. It is difficult to control film thickness with this method. Often, an adsorption step precedes electropolymerization, that is responsible for the film formation.

Immobilization of antibody by cross-linking with glutaraldehyde⁴⁶ on the sensor surface was done to make the sensor very sensitive (detection of 5 ppb) to penicillin in milk. The work of Cosnier and Innocent⁴⁷ utilized adsorption followed by electropolymerization for polymer film formation. The cationic surfactant part of anionic tyrosinase was substituted with pyrrole to form a modified monomer. This was adsorbed onto an electrode surface and was then electropolymerized.

The elimination of the electro-oxidisable interferences, ascorbate, urate, and acetaminophen by peroxidation via horseradish peroxidase, that would otherwise interfere with the amperometric determination of glucose by glucose oxidase oxidation at a vitreous carbon electrode, was accomplished by Maidan and Heller⁴⁸ using polymer films. Glucose oxidase was immobilized in an osmium-containing redox polymer with a poly(vinylpyridine) backbone and crosslinked with poly(ethylene glycol)diglycidyl ether. The reduction of flavin adenin dinucleotide (FAD) (that was bound to the glucose oxidase) to FADH₂ expedited electron turnover by the enzyme. Electron transfer to the electrode occurred via the osmium centers within the redox polymer network. A barrier layer that consisted of poly(vinylimidazole) crosslinked with ethylene glycol diglycidyl ether functioned to electrically insulate the glucose sensing layer from a horseradish peroxidase film that was crosslinked with glutaraldehyde (or by periodate oxidation), and was used to peroxidize interferences via horseradish peroxidase.

Fouling and biocompatibility

A major problem that occurs in the analysis of biological samples is electrode fouling. It is defined as electrode

surface passivation due to the adsorption of nonelectroactive species. High molecular weight substances, such as proteins, represent a major source of fouling, which gives decreased biosensor response with time.

Sasso *et al.*³⁷ addressed fouling in a biological matrix with an electropolymerized poly(1,2-DAB) film that prevented fouling of the biosensor by proteins in blood serum. Geise *et al.*⁴⁹ reported that a poly(1,3-DAB/resorcinol) covered electrode was not fouled by serum solution and the response to H₂O₂ remained identical subsequent to serum analysis. The use of an appropriate polymer film to impart biocompatibility is important in preventing interferences from reaching the electrode surface and to preclude fouling. Additionally, for *in vivo* applications, the use of a biocompatible polymeric film eliminates blood clotting as well as the immune reaction⁵⁰.

Immobilization of biocomponents

A number of techniques to immobilize a biocomponent onto an electrode surface are available including adsorption, covalent attachment, microencapsulation, gel/polymer entrapment, and crosslinking. All of these methods have been used in conjunction with polymer films. In cases where spatial resolution of different biocomponents entrapped in a polymeric film is required, such as for different microarray electrodes, the immobilization process is facilitated by the use of electropolymerization techniques. Griffith *et al.*⁵¹ demonstrated that greater amount of enzymes could be entrapped by nonconducting electropolymerized poly(*o*-phenylenediamine) film. A variety of different biocomponents have been immobilized in polymeric films and used in construction of biosensors. These include glucose oxidase, choline oxidase, L-amino acid oxidase, galactose oxidase, cholesterol oxidase, catalase, lactate oxidase, uricase, tyrosinase, pyruvate oxidase, antibody, virus, and chemoreceptors. Mulchandani and Pan⁵² constructed a ferrocene-conjugated *m*-phenylenediamine conducting polymer-incorporated peroxidase biosensor with a glassy carbon electrode for measuring analytes with high selectivity, sensitivity, and good precision. Recently, Yon Him and Lowe⁵³ have further improved the biosensors by covalently attaching 3-carboxymethylpyrrole to the lysyl residues of glucose oxidase and copolymerized this moiety with unmodified pyrrole. An increased response to glucose due to the improved immobilized reactivity as compared to *N*-derivatized pyrrole-modified glucose oxidase and improved long-term biosensor stability were realized.

A solution of antibody, bovine serum albumin (BSA), and glutaraldehyde in aqueous solution was cast via a screen-

ing method onto dual gold electrodes that were located on electrode chips to construct an antibody biosensor⁵⁴. This produced a protein film on the electrode surface. Electrode chips that do not contain antibody were prepared in a manner analogous to the above procedure. These enabled the use of a differential circuit that provided subtraction of background, as well as non-specific binding. Two biosensors based upon antibodies were prepared. The first one used human immunoglobulin G (hIgG) and a direct dose-response curve was produced when dilution of goat serum containing anti-hIgG was used to compete the hIgG. A second biosensor used anti-hIgG, which produced a direct dose-response curve when competing with hIgG.

Conclusions

Polymer films are incorporated in biosensors to facilitate electron transfer from biocomponent to the electrode surface, for the incorporation of mediators and in the immobilization of enzymes. The polymeric materials give stability and remove interference to a great extent. Use of polymer in almost all the biosensors is therefore obvious. However, judicious choice of the polymeric materials and the methods are very important since different polymers have different blocking capacities for the analytes.

Knowledge of possible electron transfer pathways plays an important role in the development of amperometric biosensors with improved operation characteristics. Obviously, a compromise has to be found between tight immobilization of all sensor components on the electrode surface and the need to maintain a sufficient high flexibility to allow proper approach of redox centres involved in the electron-transfer chain to obtain a high rate constant of the overall reaction. Future work will be directed towards production of reagentless amperometric enzyme electrodes with low working potential, decreased influence of the oxygen partial pressure and interfering compounds, simultaneously taking into account the need for mass production and miniaturization.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.S.P.) gratefully acknowledges C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for awarding a Senior Research Fellowship and the other (P.S.) acknowledges A.I.C.T.E., New Delhi, for awarding a research grant.

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